

Os (VIII) Catalysed Oxidation of Glycollic Acid by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate (III)

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Manuscript received 24 July 1972 ; accepted 4 June 1974.

The rate of reaction is found to be proportional to the concentration of glycollic acid, Os (VIII), hydroxyl ion ($[\text{OH}^-] < 0.25M$), but independent of concentration of hexacyanoferrate (III). The reaction has been studied at different temperatures and the value of ΔE , PZ and ΔS^\ddagger are found to be 11.00 k. cal. mole⁻¹, 2.80×10^7 min⁻¹ at 40° and -25.36 e.u. respectively. A mechanism based on acid anion-Os (VIII) complex formation has been suggested.

KINETIC studies on oxidation of a variety of substances, both organic and inorganic, by hexacyanoferrate (III) have been undertaken by many workers. Unless a catalyst is employed these reactions are either extremely slow or do not proceed at all. The most widely investigated catalyst is Os (VIII).

Among several compounds the kinetics of oxidation of 3-mercaptopropionic acid¹, 2-mercaptoethanol², thioacetamide³, thiourea³, ascorbic acid⁴, acetaldehyde⁵, mandelic acid⁶ have been investigated.

A review of the literature shows that oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) has not received much attention. The present paper deals with the results on the oxidation of glycollic acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) catalysed by Os (VIII).

Experimental

Materials : OsO₄ (Johnson & Mathey) and hexacyanoferrate (III) (AnalaR sample) Glycollic acid (Riedel) were used. All other chemicals were chemically pure.

Catalyst : It was obtained by dissolving known weight of OsO₄ in KOH solution (.05 M).

Reaction mixture containing the requisite quantities of glycollic acid, OsO₄, NaOH were prepared in the reaction vessel. The reaction mixture and hexacyanoferrate (III) solutions were thermostated, for about 20 mins to attain experimental temp. 35°. A known volume of hexacyanoferrate (III) was then transferred to the reaction mixture and aliquots were removed from time to time and analysed for unconsumed hexacyanoferrate (III) with Klett-Sumersons Photoelectric Colorimeter within the wave length range of 400-450 nm. Variations of the concentration of hexacyanoferrate (III) were well within the range of Beer's law ($1.6 \times 10^{-3}M - 5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$). No absorption was evident due to other species.

Results

Formaldehyde and formic acid were identified as the products of oxidation. As the presence of air does not change the form of rate law, no attempt was made to remove oxygen from the reaction system.

The effect of varying (i) hexacyanoferrate (III) concentration, (ii) reductant concentration, (iii) catalyst concentration and (iv) alkaline concentration on the rate constant was investigated and the results are presented in Tables 1 to 3. At low hydroxyl ion concentration [$< .25 M$] rate follows first order. However it becomes zero order at $[\text{OH}^-] > .25 M$ (Table 4). It is observed that change in ionic strength as a result of addition of either K₂SO₄ or KNO₃ affects the rate constants showing a positive salt effect.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF HEXACYANOFERRATE (III).

[Glycollate] = $4.66 \times 10^{-3}M$, [OsO ₄] = $4.117 \times 10^{-5}M$ [NaOH] = .14M, temp. 35°, $\mu = .32 M$					
[Fe(CN) ₆] ⁻³ × 10 ⁴ M	2.33	3.50	4.66	5.83	6.99
k ₀ × 10 ⁵ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	1.65	1.86	1.50	1.60	1.36

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF REDUCTANT.

[Hexacyanoferrate (III)] = $4.66 \times 10^{-4}M$, [OsO ₄] = $4.117 \times 10^{-5}M$ [NaOH] = .14M, temp. 35°, $\mu = .32M$					
[Glycollate] × 10 ³ M	4.66	3.50	2.33	1.165	0.58
[k ₀ × 10 ⁵ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	1.50	1.11	0.90	0.52	0.32
k ₀ × 10 ² min ⁻¹	0.32	0.32	0.39	0.45	0.56
[Glycollate]					

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF CATALYST.

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = $4.66 \times 10^{-4}M$, [NaOH] = .14M [Glycollate] = $4.66 \times 10^{-3}M$, temp. 35°, $\mu = .32M$					
[OsO ₄] × 10 ⁵ M	2.74	3.43	4.12	4.80	5.49
k ₀ × 10 ⁵ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	0.90	1.27	1.50	2.00	2.35
k ₀ min ⁻¹	0.33	0.37	0.36	0.42	0.42
[OsO ₄]					

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF ALKALI.

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = $4.66 \times 10^{-4}M$, [Glycollate] = $4.66 \times 10^{-3}M$, [OsO ₄] = $4.117 \times 10^{-5}M$, temp. 35°, $\mu = .5 M$								
[NaOH] × 10 ³ M	3.50	10.50	17.50	24.50	31.5	35.0	38.5	42.0
k ₀ × 10 ⁵ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	1.06	1.43	1.60	1.80	1.80	1.82	1.81	1.79

Discussion

Since one electron transfer is involved in the system the possible existence of free radical intermediate in the oxidation of organic compounds by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) is expected, but experimental evidence does not indicate presence of free radicals, hence mechanism based on formation of a soluble complex between acid anion and Os (VIII) is suggested. Since uncatalysed reaction does not proceed at all and hexacyanoferrate (III) is consumed without taking part in rate law, it is assumed that the hexacyanoferrate (III) does not react directly until after the rate determining step.

The alkali dependence of the reaction indicates that acid-anions are the entities oxidised. The mechanism proposed involves formation of complex between acid anion and osmate VIII ion, furnished by action of OsO₄ and KOH. This complex then rapidly decomposes to give aldehyde and osmate (VI) ion, subsequently Os (VIII) ion is then regenerated by oxidation of osmate (VI) ion by hexacyanoferrate (III). This observation is in full agreement with that of Mayell⁷ that hexacyanoferrate is effective in oxidising Os (VI) to Os (VIII).

On the basis of this mechanism and applying steady state approximation, we get

$$R = -\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-3} = \frac{k_2 k_3 [\text{Glycollate}][\text{Os(VIII)}][\text{OH}^-]}{k_{-2} + k_3 [\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{-3} = \frac{k_2 [\text{Glycollate}][\text{Os(VIII)}][\text{OH}^-]}{\frac{k_{-2}}{k_3} + [\text{OH}^-]}$$

Assuming [OH⁻] to be low, such that $\frac{k_{-2}}{k_3} > [\text{OH}^-]$ and

$\left\{ \frac{k_{-2}}{k_3} + [\text{OH}^-] \right\} \approx \frac{k_{-2}}{k_3}$, the rate law (5) approximates to

$$R = \frac{k_2 k_3}{k_{-2}} [\text{Glycollate}][\text{Os(VIII)}][\text{OH}^-] \quad \dots(6)$$

At high [OH⁻], [OH⁻] ≫ $\frac{k_{-2}}{k_3}$ such that $\left\{ \frac{k_{-2}}{k_3} + [\text{OH}^-] \right\} \approx [\text{OH}^-]$,

the rate law (5) reduces to

$$R = \frac{k_2 [\text{Glycollate}][\text{Os(VIII)}][\text{OH}^-]}{[\text{OH}^-]} = k_2 [\text{Glycollate}][\text{Os(VIII)}] \quad \dots(7)$$

Thus equations (6) and (7) explain the experimental results i. e. first order and zero-order dependence of the rate on [OH⁻] at low and high hydroxyl ion concentration respectively.

More negative value of ΔS* than expected supports eq. (2) as the rate determining step, as two ions combine to give a bigger complex ion resulting thereby in the loss of freedom of motion; positive salt effect further lends support to the mechanistic steps, suggesting reaction between two similar charges.

Acknowledgement

One of us (G. C. S.) is thankful to U. G. C., India, for a junior research fellowship. We also thank Professor R. C. Kapoor for his encouragement and interest.

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